

THE ELEMENTARY PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF X-RAY FILMS AND PLATES

MILLARD B. HODGSON
Rochester, N. Y.

THE EMULSION

A photographic plate consists essentially of a sensitive emulsion coated on glass. This emulsion is, of course, coated while in a liquid state and dried down in a layer which is about one-thousandth of an inch thick in the average *x*-ray plate or film.

Fundamentally the emulsion consists of a suspension of silver bromide in gelatine. It is prepared by adding together in a gelatine solution silver nitrate and potassium bromide in proper proportions, the essential reaction being that the silver unites with the bromine to form silver bromide. Were this reaction to take place in a strictly liquid solution, the silver bromide crystals formed would sink to the bottom, forming a white precipitate. In the gelatinous solution, however, they remain in suspension and form, after coating, the sensitive units of the photographic plate or film.

THE PHYSICS OF EXPOSURE AND DEVELOPMENT

Silver bromide, as found in the photographic emulsion, occurs in the form of more or less perfect crystals belonging to the cubic system. In the average plate they are usually in the form of thin, fragmentary slabs of various shapes, a great many of them being triangular. Some of these formations are shown in Fig. 1, which is a micrograph made at a magnification of about 1,000 diameters. These silver bromide crystals in the finished photographic plate are sensitive to light. They are also sensitive to

x-rays and other forms of energy, whether applied in the form of heat, friction or chemical change. They are "sensitive" in the sense that they will record the relative amount of action on them by any of these agencies. The reaction which occurs in a silver bromide crystal when exposed to light or *x*-rays, however, is so small that it cannot be measured by any direct physical or chemical means. By treating exposed emulsion, however, with solutions called "developers", the bromine is removed from the grains affected by exposure, leaving metallic silver. Reduction of each grain is a steady transition from silver bromide to silver, the bromine being taken up by the developer. The grains not affected by the exposure, and hence undeveloped, are then dissolved in a suitable solution. Changes occurring in the development of silver bromide grains are shown in Fig. 2.

It has been found that a crystal which has been exposed to light so that it becomes developable is entirely developable, provided sufficient time is given for the action of the solution. This can be seen by inspection of the micrograph in Fig. 3, which shows a single grain at two stages of its development.

The silver grains of the visible image in the negative are thus formed in practically the same space occupied by the parent crystals. This is illustrated in Fig 4, which is a micrograph of the *same* grains, before and after development. During development the reduced silver is deposited in ultra-microscopic particles, so that the completed grain appears like a collection of black soot embedded in the gelatine. When this phenomenon is watched under the microscope the transition seems very similar to the popping of a kernel of corn, for in most cases the shape of the original crystal is somewhat distorted.

THE LATENT IMAGE

The reaction which takes place when light strikes the silver bromide crystal is generally termed "the formation

of the latent image", and there are numerous theories which seek to explain the nature of the change. Mees¹ gives figures on the approximate amount of energy involved in forming a latent image in a high speed photographic plate, and deduces from these computations that the energy involved in making a silver bromide crystal developable is of the order of that involved in the liberation of an electron from one molecule of silver bromide. It is, of course, too small to measure by any known direct laboratory methods.

THE DEVELOPER

The development of the latent image in a photographic plate is a complex chemical reaction; for in addition to the delicate materials in the plate itself, there enters into the reaction four other distinct compounds, each in solution. Considering then, that there are seven primary substances entering into the process of development, from which there are formed additional compounds, one can easily see the necessity of confining the possible reactions to a minimum by the use of standard materials and standard methods.

Broadly speaking, a developer consists of four essential constituents, as follows:

- (1) A "reducer"
- (2) A preservative
- (3) An accelerator
- (4) A fog restrainer

The reducer is usually an organic chemical like Elon or Hydrochinon or Pyro. Without it, the solution would not develop the image. Being a reducer, it follows that it is useful in the developer only so long as its ability to take up oxygen is retained. It, therefore, follows that useless oxidation of the reducer by exposure of the developer to air should be guarded against.

It is the function of the preservative to keep the useless oxidation of the reducer to a minimum. For this work

¹ C. E. K. Mees—*Journal of the American Chemical Society*, November, 1913.

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sodium sulphite is by far the most widely satisfactory chemical. If, however, only these two materials were put into a developer, the solution would take an infinitely long time to act. To accelerate this process it is necessary that the solution be alkaline. Sodium carbonate is quite satisfactory for this, and in addition is cheap and easy to secure.

But these three materials in one solution, while they would cause the development of those grains which were exposed, would, if allowed to act for the time necessary to develop the image, also cause the development of other grains which were not exposed. It is to check this tendency that the restrainer must be added. The function of this restrainer, which is usually potassium bromide, is to stop the development of fog, or those grains which are in such a state that the slightest action of the developing solution will start their reduction.

It is necessary, of course, in a solution designed for development, that the amounts of these constituents must be properly balanced in their relations to one another. There must be just sufficient quantity of reducer to perform the work necessary, sufficient sulphite to preserve this amount of reducing agent while not in use, a minimum of carbonate to make the reaction time normal and a minimum quantity of restrainer that will prevent a reduction of grains which have not been intentionally exposed.

After the reaction of development is complete the plate should be rinsed carefully before proceeding to the operation of fixing, in order to remove developer held in the gelatine. At this stage the plate still contains, in addition to the developed silver image, the balance of the silver bromide which has been unaffected by exposure. Being opaque, it must be removed.

THE FIXING BATH

The fixing bath, too, is a combination of chemicals in solution which is somewhat analogous to the developer. The fundamental material entering into it is "Hypo" or

sodium thiosulphate—which, in solution, is a solvent for silver bromide. Unfortunately, in combination with developer which may be left after rinsing, it will cause the deposition of colloidal silver. This is the familiar “dichroic fog”, which appears as a red stain by transmitted light and as a green one by reflected light. It is necessary, therefore, to add to the fixing bath a chemical which will counteract this possible action or “kill” the developer. Acetic acid has been found to perform this function quite satisfactorily.

In the fixing bath, as well as developer, it is also necessary to add sodium sulphate as a preservative, not only for the Hypo itself, to prevent its being acted upon by the other materials in this solution, but to prevent the oxidation of developer carried over into the fixing bath before it is “killed” by the acetic acid.

Finally, there is usually added a hardening agent which will tend to toughen the gelatine so it will stand a thorough washing in water of average temperature. This hardening agent is, in most cases, an alum. White potassium alum has been found most satisfactory.

DRYING

It should be remembered that the making of a photographic negative is not completed until the developed emulsion is dried, for unless this seemingly simple operation is correctly carried out the care in the previous operations may all be in vain.

During the drying of a photographic emulsion on glass or other solid support there is a gradual contraction of the gelatine vertically in the direction of the support until it is, when dry, scarcely one-twentieth of its wet thickness. This, of course, results in a series of strain adjustments, which must proceed at a uniform rate if the original image is not to be distorted. The drying of all negatives, therefore, should proceed at a uniform rate — in an atmosphere where there is no likelihood of contamination.

In all operations—exposure or formation of the latent image, development, fixation and drying—the routine methods should be standardized to preclude the introduction of disturbing factors.

The writer wishes to acknowledge his indebtedness to Mr. A. P. H. Trivelli for the interesting micrograph shown in Figure 4.

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EASTMAN KODAK CO.
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FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2

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2

FIGURE 3

FIGURE 4